

Fig. 1

addition method. The results are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1 (curve c ; B=blank).

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Nitrite (Nitrogen Dioxide)

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WE report here a spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrite/nitrogen dioxide by azo dye formation. Acidified *p*-rosaniline hydrochloride diazotised with nitrite/nitrogen dioxide and coupled with *N*-1-naphthylethylenediamine

dihydrochloride yields a red-violet dye which absorbs at 560 nm. Taking advantage of this reaction a sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of nitrite/nitrogen dioxide.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for making the following solutions unless otherwise specified: sodium nitrite, 6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in 0.001 *M* NaOH; *N*-1-naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride, 0.1% solution in water; *p*-rosaniline hydrochloride, 0.04% solution in 0.72 *M* HCl; alkaline sodium arsenite, 1 g of arsenous oxide dissolved in water and 100 ml of 1.2 *M* NaOH and the volume made up 2 dm^3 .

A Hilger and Watts H 700 spectrophotometer with 1 cm cell was used for absorbance measurement.

Procedure: 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml of the sodium nitrite solutions were placed in a series of 50 ml volumetric flasks. The *p*-rosaniline hydrochloride solution (2 ml) was added, shaken well and then the *N*-1-naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride solution (0.5 ml) was added to each flask. The full colour developed within 30 min and the absorbance for 560 nm was measured against a reagent blank. A linear absorbance concentration profile was obtained (Beer's law) in the concentration range of 0.04 – 0.40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of nitrite.

In another experiment 0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 4 ml of the sodium nitrite solutions were placed in the sodium arsenite solution (10 ml) and the experiment was repeated as before. Absorbances were little affected by the presence of sodium arsenite for lower nitrite concentrations.

Results and Discussion

p-Rosaniline hydrochloride when acidified with hydrochloric acid reacts with nitrite to yield a diazo compound which when coupled with *N*-1-naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride produces a red-violet dye having an absorption maximum at 560 nm.

The effect of varying the quantities of the diazotising agent and coupling agent was studied. 2 ml of 0.04% acidified dye and 0.5 ml of 0.1% *N*-1-naphthylethylenediamine hydrochloride were found to be best for full colour development. Reproducibility of the method was checked by taking several samples of same concentration of nitrite and the standard deviation was found to be ± 0.009 . Sensitivity determined from the slope of the calibration graph was found to be 0.833 absorbance unit per $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity 0.0012 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

NOTES

Interferences due to sulphite, sulphide and a few metallic ions which are generally present as pollutants were investigated. Interferences due to 50 μg each of Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} and Cr^{III} were negligible. Addition of 0.5 ml of 0.1 *N* EDTA to nitrite solution eliminated interference due to metallic ions. A 4 μg sulphide could be tolerated^{1,2}. Sulphite interferes to a lesser extent, interference due to 25 μg sodium sulphite was negligible³.

The method was extended to the estimation of nitrogen dioxide in air after fixing it in alkaline sodium arsenite solution. Air samples were collected at different ratios (0.5, 0.75 and 1.2 $\text{dm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$)

for about 5 h and analysed by the standard and the present methods. The experiment was repeated by collecting air samples in two different impingers containing alkaline sodium arsenite at the rate of 0.4 $\text{dm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$ for 1 h. Concentration of nitrogen dioxide in air estimated was found to be 0.01 ppm by the present method which was comparable to that obtained by the standard methods.

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